

Analyzing Online Learning Behavior and Effectiveness of Blended Learning using Students' Accessing Timeline

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Abstract

Fundamental courses in most engineering curricula usually retain high enrollment rate, yet they induce several challenges on the course delivery such as learner differentiation, low interactions between learners and instructors, and thus leading to poor studying performance. This paper investigates and analyzes the effectiveness of applying a blended learning approach to overcome such important challenges. We applied a blended learning approach to the design and delivery of an engineering mathematics course to the first-year engineering students at a university in Thailand. The students' online learning behavior and learning performance have been analyzed using learning analytics and visualization techniques, resulting in two groups: i) Attentive students, who learned the online materials in parallel with the contents taught in classroom; and ii) Bypass students, who accessed merely online tests just before the course ending. The analysis found that most high performers were attentive students, while the majority of low performers were bypass students. The correlation between the student performance and the ratio of attentive to bypass students could be used as fundamental factors to evaluate the effectiveness of the blended learning approach for courses in the similar setting.

1 Introduction

Principal engineering subjects such as mathematics, physics and chemistry have been standing courses in most undergraduate engineering curricula for early-year students. Those course contents are basic knowledge essential for engineering and rarely change overtime. Blended learning is considered an effective pedagogy improvement over typical classroom methods since it can provide students extended learning supports by incorporating online learning tools and materials. To-date there exist several models to implement and deliver blended learning depending on the nature of the course and the learning environment (Blended Learning Universe, 2020). A 'Station Rotation model' rotates students through stations where at least one of them is online learning which is suitable for courses that have lab works or activities. 'Flex model' has online learning as a backbone while teachers provide support and instructions as needed. 'Flipped-classroom model' requires students to learn from online lectures and join the classroom for activities. 'Wrapped course' (Bruff et al., 2013), is a model where instructors "wrap" their courses around existing MOOCs. Students participate in part or in whole in a MOOC hosted at another institution, while teachers conduct face-to-face, classroom interactions. 'Online-as-a-supplementary' model uses face-to-face classroom as a core delivery while students are encouraged to study from online as a supplementary.

This research studied an engineering mathematics course which applied 'online-as-a-supplementary' approach. The online materials were designed as a MOOC course mimicking the classroom content and contained quizzes and assessments. The instructors announced that the MOOC score will be used as incentive scores, which counts as a part of the class final scores in order to promote student's usage of the MOOC. This strategy is effective to ensure students' engagement but some students merely participated to gain the incentive score without an intention to learn from it. Therefore, it is difficult for the instructors to evaluate the effectiveness of the blended learning.

Our research investigated student's behaviors in terms of efforts spent and accessing timeline on online materials in order to identify student's learning intentions and to evaluate the effectiveness of blended learning. The study revealed that most high performance students appropriately adopted the new methodology as they spent considerable efforts on online materials along with the classroom teaching period. On the other hand, most low performance students were stuck with traditional classroom teaching and attended online

assessments just before the course ending period aiming to gain the incentive score. The different ratio between 2 intention groups can infer the effectiveness of the application of blended learning.

This paper is organized as follows. First, the background and structure of selected course are described. Second, the instructors' concerns on student's learning intentions and effectiveness of blended learning are explained. Next, the analysis results and recommendations for blended learning instructional design are discussed. Finally, the conclusion is presented.

2 Applying Blended Learning to Engineering Mathematics II

2.1 Background

'Engineering Mathematic II' is a fundamental engineering course in the undergraduate engineering curriculum of Kasetsart University. It is a standing course scheduled for the first-year students. The number of enrolled students is approximately 1,500 yearly. The course content covers advanced mathematics e.g. vector and quadric surface in 3D, partial derivative, multiple integrals and vector calculus. Because of the challenging contents and the variety of background knowledge, certain students struggled to catch up. The instructors also had trouble adapting their pace to ensure that students understand the contents well in the large classrooms setting. As a result, a number of students failed or unenrolled from the course. The course has been offered every semester for reattempting.

Thus, the instructors adopted the online-as-a-supplementary blended learning model, and published the online course on the Thai MOOC platform (www.thaimooc.org) in 2018 with the following objectives:

- Students who miss or do not catch up in class can access the course and replay as they wish.
- Students who seek to extend their understanding from the classroom content can find additional examples.
- Instructors can use certain online materials in classroom teaching e.g. 3D animations or quizzes.
- Students can practice mathematical problem solving to prepare for their exams. The online materials also provide valid resolutions with detailed explanation.
- Students can download classroom sheets and extra materials that the instructors prepared, e.g., formula summary or cheat sheet.

2.2 Course Structure and Delivery Method

The online materials were designed to mimic the classroom content, which comprised 5 chapters with the total of 165 video clips, 41 readings and 250 problems. Each chapter started with a pre-test, followed by an introduction video and contents (videos and readings), then ended with a quiz session and a post-test respectively. All videos had the duration between 2 – 10 minutes. Most readings were lecture slides that the instructors used in the classroom teaching. Problems on pre-tests, post-tests and quizzes had the same difficulty level. The grading policy were defined to consider the scores from classroom exams and from the online quizzes. The proportion can be broken down as shown in Figure 1a.

The course was launched in the inter-semester 2018 during June to August. There were 2 classrooms with 168 and 113 students. Most students were freshmen from the Faculty of Engineering. The online materials were hosted in Thai MOOC platform, based on Open edX. The suggested online learning effort was 5 hours/week with the total of 45 hours. The instructors spent their first session informing their classes about the online materials, its objectives including scoring policy as well as how to enroll and learn online. Throughout the semester, the instructors consistently motivated students to watch videos for additional detail on what he/she had taught. Students were encouraged to practice online problems when the instructors finished the lecture of each chapter. A week before the final exam, the instructors advised students to practice the MOOC post-test to get a direction of the final exam problems.

2.3 Learning Intentions and Blended Learning's Effectiveness: the Concerns

The instructors promoted the utilization of the online materials by including a score of the MOOC as 25% of the total course score. This incentive scheme is commonly used to stimulate student's engagement on online content. Surprisingly, to the best of our knowledge, there was no study on learning behaviors affected by such a scheme.

The instructors had two concerns:

- 1) Using incentives unavoidably diverse students' learning intentions. There were 2 groups of students; 'Attentive students' who utilized the online materials in order to gain more understanding, and 'Bypass students' who merely focused on earning the incentive score without an intention to learn from it. These learning intentions can be linked to the classic learning approaches introduced by Duff et al (2004): i) 'deep approach' which refers to behavior of students who seek to understand, ii) 'surface approach' which is based on behavior of memorization, and iii) 'strategic approach' which refers to student with the attitude to achieve the highest grades. Since the mathematics course is hardly memorizable, the 'attentive' and 'bypass' intentions concerned by the instructors in this course are associated with 'deep' and 'strategic' learning approaches in Duff's research accordingly. The instructors had a requirement to distinguish students by these intentions to be able to understand the student's nature and to adapt delivery strategy appropriately.
- 2) Since it was the first time to introduce the blended learning approach in their classes, the instructors needed a method to evaluate its effectiveness. In our review of literature, many researches on blended learning evaluation were based on qualitative approaches which using questionnaires and surveys. Bowyer and Chambers (2017) concluded a blended learning evaluation framework from many researchers containing elements and a rubric to measure its effectiveness in multiple dimensions. Israel (2015) studied a model of integrating MOOC into traditional classrooms and analyzed passing rates between different categories of learners. Kenny and Newcombe (2011) compared the score difference between students in a blended and a non-blended learning environment. As far as we know, there was no evaluation that were quantitative or based on student's behavior in previous research.

We believed the analysis of specific students' learning behaviors could be an indicator of their learning intentions and could reflect the effectiveness of the blended learning. In a blended learning environment, where the learning pace was controlled by the instructors, attentive students accessed the online materials during the period that the topics were taught in the classroom, and spent an appropriate amount of time in learning and problem practice. On the other hand, bypass students accessed the scored tests near the deadline, and spent less effort since they may know the correct answers from their friends. In other words, attentive students fully utilized blended learning while bypass students mostly depend on classroom teaching and rarely benefit from the online materials. If we could identify the relationship between students' performance and attentive / bypass student behaviors, we could verify the effectiveness of blended learning.

3 Analysis of Online Learning Behavior and Blended Learning Effectiveness

The research studied student behaviors from their efforts and accessing timeline. The event logs on Thai MOOC were passed through the ETL process and analyzed in combination with learner’s performance. This section explored general statistics and the relationship between the learner’s behaviors and their performances.

Figure 1. Course score policy (a) and Student performance distribution (b).

3.1 Score Distribution: MOOC Scores vs. Final Grades

Figure 1b illustrates the number of students by their final performances. The instructors partitioned student’s final grades with normal distribution as shown in the orange line. The average online scores for each grade were plotted along. We found a direct variation between average online score and final grades. Note that there were only 2 students with the ‘F’ grade which were insufficient to make a meaningful analysis, and thus excluded from the study.

3.2 Student Effort Analysis

Student efforts were analyzed for each grade in two aspects: 1) the number of actions a student performed, and 2) the duration a student spent on online materials. For the first aspect, we calculated the average number of actions a student in each grade performed on problems and videos. The action type for problems was answer submission, while the video actions included all media controls i.e. play, seek, pause, stop and speed change. With the incentive score offering, most students had completed all scored problems and since most problems allowed only one attempt, the average number of actions on problems among students were in the close range (denoted by the blue bars of Figure 2a). The blue dotted trendline with a linear decline pattern (R-squared=0.87) indicates students with higher grades have a higher action rate.

Considering the second aspect, i.e., the duration spent, the timestamp of the first action and the last action that a student performed consequently on each topic were calculated and cumulated. There were cases that students left their PC or browser without logging out which caused the duration to overrun (too long). We replaced such values with an upper bound duration that the instructor expected a student to spend on that material which, for this course, were 2x of video’s length for videos and 15 minutes for problems. A polynomial trend line was applied on the average duration on the problem shown as the blue dotted lines in Figure 2b. The trend line presented an obvious decline pattern (R-squared=0.93) illustrating that high performance students spent more effort on a problem practice compared to low performance students.

Figure 2. Student's Effort by Grades

The effort trend lines on video (the orange dotted lines) fluctuated. The average durations spent on videos among student of various grades showed insignificant difference when compared to the actual video length (average of 464 seconds). This is because of very few student engagements on videos. A majority of students (83%) watched less than 25% of total videos. Almost half of students (44%) did not watch any video at all. This concurred with some research that low attention in video content is a common student's behavior. Gil and Williams (2017) revealed that the average video watching duration is 3 minutes. Ho et al., (2014) found a similar rate of content engagement; 56% of students engaged about a quarter of content while 35% never visited at all. The results illustrated that the more students utilized the online problems, the better learning performance they gained. This is correlated with the result of Albrecht et al., (2018) which studied blended learning in an introductory programming course.

3.3 Online Material Access Timeline Analysis

To enable us to analyze online material access timeline, the number of students accessing a courseware in each chapter grouped by date was extracted. In our analysis, students were categorized into 3 groups based on their performance: high performers (A, B+ grades; n=53), middle performers (B, C+, C grades; n=147), and low performers (D+, D grades; n=63). Since the total number of students in each group were unequal, the number of daily accessing students were normalized to percentage for comparison. Polynomial equation was applied to reduce fluctuations of the original data and visualize the trend lines. We found the 6th order polynomial trend lines was the best fit with R-squared values ranged from 0.4 in early chapters to 0.84 in late chapters. Even though they were not statistically satisfied, the trend lines let us visualize and distinguish clearly the patterns among groups of students.

As the instructors regularly reminded students to watch videos and practice on the online problems, we hypothesized high access rates on videos and problems in parallel with the topic taught in the classroom for attentive students. On the other hand, we also hypothesized a high access rate near the course deadline from bypass students who tried to complete all online problems for the incentive score.

The results in Figure 3 revealed the correlation of students' accessing timeline with their performance. Our analysis considered the highest peak as the access date of each student group. The blue trend lines represent high performance students (A, B+ grades). They accessed videos and problems earlier on every chapter with the most intensive rate which match the behavior of attentive students. The gray trend lines are low performance students (D+, D grades). They accessed the online materials later especially on problems which is the behavior of bypass students.

Figure 3. Online material accessing timeline on videos (left) and on problems (right)

The midterm exam contained the content of Chapters 1 and 2. Note that problem accessing trend lines of both chapters have two humps. The first one on the same period as the topic taught in the classroom demonstrated a group of students who intended to learn from online materials. The later hump is closing to the end date illustrated another group of students who tried to complete early chapters' problems with a clear intention to gain incentive scores since those chapters were already tested in the midterm exam and would not recur on the final exam. The trend line for Chapter 3 also has two humps but was not included in our analysis since the content was taught both before and after midterm exam. The trend lines of Chapters 4 and 5 have only one

hump since the teaching was close to the end date causing students to access the chapters crowded in one period.

3.4 Blended Learning Effectiveness Analysis

From the results, the distinctive behaviors on online materials indicate clearly whether or not students had adopted the blended learning approach. The relation between these behaviors and students' performance reflects the effectiveness of blended learning. The effort analysis in Subsection 3.2 depicts that the more effort students spent on problem practicing, the better course score they gained. The online problem accessing behaviors in Subsection 3.3 also shows the correlation with student's performance. The blue trend lines of pre-midterm chapters in Figure 3 with higher first humps clearly stated that most high performers were attentive students who adopted the blended learning. On the other hand, the gray trend lines with higher second humps depict that most of the low performers were bypass students who did not adopt the blended learning approach.

The study extended further to calculate the ratio of attentive and bypass students by performances. We classified students who completed more than 50% of problems in Chapter 1 and 2 before midterm exam as 'attentive' and students who start accessing those problems after the exam as 'bypass'. Figure 4 demonstrates the ratio of attentive and bypass students by performance. Ratio of attentive students was significantly high for good performers (81% for A grade) and reduced according to the performances (17% for D grade). On the contrary, ratio of bypass students raised on lower performers.

We believe the ratio of attentive/bypass students by performance and student effort by performance can be further developed to be a behavior-base data-driven approach for evaluate effectiveness of blended learning courses in the similar setting.

Figure 4. Ratio of student intention by performance

4 Blended Learning Instructional Design: Recommendations

Founded on the analyzed results presented in the previous section together with the observation obtained during the classroom instruction, the course instructors have made the following suggestions regarding the blended learning instructional design of a similar course:

- 1) The online materials in blended learning should be laid out to complement with content the instructors teach in the classroom, not to produce as a complete course with the similar content.
- 2) For engineering-related courses, self-practice problems with solutions in online materials can help promote student's learning.
- 3) To effectively implement the incentive score strategy, the number of available online problems should be properly considered and be separated into problems for learning and practice purpose, and problems for assessment purpose. Students should be encouraged to work on the practice problems without any restriction in terms of time and number of attempts, while the assessment problems should be randomized with the limitation on the number of attempts and the time to ensure a valid evaluation.

5 Conclusion

This paper explored a fundamental engineering course that applied blended learning with an incentive score from online materials. This strategy was shown to be effective for promoting the online material utilization. However, it unavoidably diversified students into 2 groups: i) 'attentive students' who utilized the online materials according to the designed approach, and ii) 'bypass students' who relied on classroom teaching and took advantage of the online materials merely to gain the incentive score.

The study analyzed the following specific learner's behaviors on the online materials which can indicate their learning intention: i) student's effort including the number of online actions and time spent, and ii) students' accessing timeline. The analysis result yielded two interesting online behavioral patterns of the students. The first group is the students who accessed online materials in parallel with the content taught in the classroom with reasonable amount of effort; hence matching the profile of attentive students. The other group of students completed only the provided assessment near to the course ending period with considerably less effort spent; and thus matching the bypass student's profile.

Taking student's performance into account, the research found a distinctive ratio of attentive and bypass students as follows. Low performance students had a significant ratio of bypass over attentive behavior. On the other hand, high performance students had an outstanding proportion of attentive behavior over bypass. We believe this data-driven and behavior-based approach could be applied to evaluate the effectiveness of other courses in the similar setting. Further research is required in order to establish a plausible quantitative mechanism and incorporate with traditional qualitative methods, e.g., questionnaires and surveys to enhance the effectiveness evaluation for blended learning.

6 References

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